

READINESS AND CHALLENGES OF GENERAL EDUCATION
TEACHERS ON THE IMPLEMENTATION
OF INCLUSIVE EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT

This study examined factors relating to inclusive education implementation in the Cebu Province, Philippines. A semi-structured survey was administered to 104 general education teachers from selected three special education centers to gather information on their profile, perceived readiness, and level of challenges. Descriptive and correlational analyses provided insight into teachers' experiences. While they felt prepared overall, more training was needed in collaboration skills. Profile suggested specialized inclusion training could help. Major difficulties included limited resources like specialist roles and facilities. Interestingly, readiness and challenges had a negligible link, implying multi-pronged solutions were warranted. Both improving teacher competencies and addressing resource constraints merit focus. As factors interact complexly, a comprehensive long-term approach spanning pre-service training and systemic support were recommended based on teachers' input. The findings offered a perspective on strengthening implementation. Targeted readiness development particularly in applied collaboration was identified as beneficial. Resource deficiencies emerged as serious impediments necessitating attention. A coordinated, evidence-informed strategy involving reforms at all educational levels showed promise for advancing inclusion according to study participants. Insights aimed to inform practical, sustainable solutions through a deeper understanding of realities on the ground.

Keywords: *Cebu Province, Philippines; Descriptive Correlation; General Education Teachers; Inclusion; Inclusion Challenges; Inclusive Education; Teacher Readiness; Special Education*

INTRODUCTION

The Philippines has made progress toward establishing inclusive education through policies, initiatives, and a mandate for equitable access. However, challenges remain in fully implementing differentiated practices that holistically support diverse student needs, as envisioned by the Department of Education (DepEd).

General education teachers play a crucial role in realizing inclusion but face challenges in their implementation of inclusive pedagogy. While efforts have been made to build teacher capacity through courses and development programs, research indicates more targeted support is still needed to equip educators with competencies for collaborative, differentiated instruction suitable for local contexts. Specifically, limitations in training, resources, role clarity, and attitudinal barriers complicate teachers' ability to plan and deliver lessons addressing the needs of heterogeneous classrooms. A lack of targeted professional learning leaves many teachers struggling without adaptive strategies and methods for integration and navigation of collaboration models. Insufficiencies in curriculum design further challenge planning and accommodations.

Additionally, heavy workloads and unclear delineation of responsibilities can impede teachers' provision of adequate support. Preconceptions regarding inclusion's impact may also initially breed resistance. These multidimensional challenges ultimately hamper educators' ability to holistically support diverse learner profiles as prescribed under inclusive pedagogy. To strengthen implementation, an in-depth understanding of teachers' capacity-building needs is required. Strategic recommendations must enhance competencies in differentiation, collaboration, and practical curriculum integration. Only by addressing current gaps in readiness can general educators fully drive quality inclusive learning as mandated.

Building teacher readiness, informed by relevant research insights, is therefore indispensable to furthering Philippine inclusion. Ultimately, equipping educators ensures diverse student needs are met through shared learning environments, realizing the vision of inclusive education.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The realization of inclusive education in the Philippines depends largely on teachers' readiness and ability to meet diverse student needs, as established in national policies. However, general educators may lack training for teaching in heterogeneous classrooms despite inclusive frameworks. Examining teachers' experiences and perspectives through theoretical constructs can provide valuable insights for strengthening inclusion. Self-efficacy theory and adult learning theory offer useful lenses for understanding issues surrounding teacher professional development for inclusion.

Self-efficacy Theory by Albert Bandura (1997). Self-efficacy pertains to teachers' confidence in their own skills and competence across ability levels. Research shows higher self-efficacy positively impacts implementation of inclusive practices through greater effort, persistence and adaptive teaching. Practical experience and targeted learning aimed at pedagogical competence have been found to bolster self-efficacy. Adult learning Theory by Malcom Knowles (1984). This recognizes teachers learn best through collaborative, experiential opportunities tailored to their needs and contexts. In-service teachers require meaningful, self-directed professional development to develop new inclusive skills. Traditional trainings are often insufficient for diverse adult learners. Workplace-focused learning allowing choice and active experimentation optimizes relevance and uptake of strategies.

Together, these theories highlight the importance of internal teacher factors like self-efficacy as well as external support systems for capacity building. Deeper analysis of practitioner viewpoints can offer direction for more effective learning programs informed by strengths, needs and classroom realities. Understanding opportunities and barriers through teachers' lived experiences aims to

strengthen implementation of Philippines' inclusive education agenda as laid out in related laws and policies. Targeted strategies have potential to better equip educators as drivers of inclusive reform.

Figure 1. Theoretical Framework

In the context of the Philippines, the laws and policies aim to lay the groundwork for inclusion but their success relies significantly on general educators' readiness and ability to implement inclusive practices. RA 11650, RA 10533 and RA 9442 establish the rights of students with disabilities to

participate in mainstream settings and receive appropriate support. However, effectively realizing inclusion in schools and classrooms depends largely on teachers.

At the implementation level, DepEd policies provide high-level guidance for inclusion but teachers must navigate the complex realities of inclusive classrooms. DepEd Order 44 s. 2021 outlines inclusive programs and strategies but general educators may struggle with differentiating instruction to meet diverse needs as intended. Similarly, DepEd Order 21 s. 2021 and DepEd Memo 054 s. 2023 establish frameworks for transitioning and special education but challenges can arise for teachers in operationalizing learner-centered, ability-based approaches.

While these acts and issuances form the basis for inclusion, gaps may exist between policies and ground-level practice from the teacher's perspective. Examining educators' experiences and capacity development needs is important to strengthen implementation. Insights into challenges, opportunities, strengths and realities in heterogeneous classrooms can offer direction for more effective support to build teacher competencies, as they are central to driving inclusive reform visions established in Philippine laws and policies.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Several studies examined teacher readiness for inclusion in different international contexts. Myronova et al. (2021) investigated higher education instructors in Ukraine and found lack of understanding about core inclusive concepts like individualized learning and diversity. Preconceived biases against students with special needs were also reported. These knowledge and attitude gaps impede competent, student-centered pedagogy required for inclusion.

Similarly, Zegeye (2022) noted Ethiopian primary teachers overall expressed lower self-ratings of preparedness to teach diverse learners. Variations occurred based on years of experience, implying classroom exposure bolsters inclusive skills over time. However, pre-service training curricula were identified as inadequate to foster relevant competencies. Without targeted support addressing identified weaknesses, general educators struggle to operationalize inclusive principles.

Specific to learning disabilities, Seman et al. (2021) surveyed Malaysian mainstream teachers and determined satisfactory cognitive understanding of inclusion policies, but more ambivalence towards full acceptance of varied class compositions. Continual professional development appears needed to close the disparity between theoretical comprehension and willingness to apply inclusive methods in real classrooms.

Studies also evaluated African contexts. Adams et al. (2023) found Ghanaian teachers used some responsive adaptations like flexible pre-teaching and multi-modal instruction. However, resource constraints inhibited the extent of individualization possible given student needs. Additional systemic support may be required to optimize educator effort.

Gyamfi and Yeboah (2022) corroborated knowledge, understanding, skills and attitudes influencing Ghanaian teacher self-assessments of competence. Factors like prior specialized training augmented inclusive self-efficacy. Where pre-service preparation lacked, perpetuating gaps in implementation readiness occurred.

In the Philippines, Moon (2023) and Logroño and Gongora (2023) reported positive general educator perceptions but still advocated ongoing educational upgrades. De La Peña et al. (2023) highlighted technology as potentially enhancing outcomes depending on individual teacher traits like qualifications mediating technology selection and use.

The literature consistently highlights that teacher-specific factors interact with complex student diversity in shaping the multidimensional challenges of inclusive implementation. Individual

variations in teachers' backgrounds, experiences, attitudes and skillsets determine their perceived and actual readiness levels. At the same time, the heterogeneous and evolving needs presented by learners with diverse profiles strain educators' capacities.

To address these interrelated but multi-layered barriers, the studies recommend ongoing professional learning programs tailored to teachers' pre-existing abilities and classroom realities. By continuously adapting support to match evolving student requirements while building upon teachers' strengths, data-driven and contextualized andragogical approaches appear most conducive to strengthening competencies over time. This customized, job-embedded learning model shows promise for enabling the systemic transformations envisioned under inclusive education reforms, according to analyses across international contexts. With targeted capacity building calibrated to teachers' dynamic instructional environments, inclusive policies may be progressively realized in practice.

THE RESEARCH PROBLEM

This research assessed the readiness and challenges encountered by the general education teachers on the implementation of inclusive education at the identified SPED centers in Cebu Province, Philippines for the school year 2022-2023 as basis for action plans.

Specifically, it sought answers to the following sub-problems:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1. age and gender,
 - 1.2. highest educational attainment,
 - 1.3. field of specialization,
 - 1.4. length of service, and
 - 1.5. relevant trainings and seminars attended?
2. What is the level of readiness of the respondents towards the implementation of inclusive education?
3. What is the level of challenges encountered by the respondents on the implementation of inclusive education?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the readiness and challenges encountered by the respondents on the implementation of inclusive education?
5. Based on the findings of the study, what action plan can be proposed?

1. Statement of the Null Hypothesis

Based on the objectives of the study, the following null hypothesis was tested at 0.05 level of significance. Ho: There is no significant relationship between the readiness and challenges encountered by the respondents on the implementation of inclusive education.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

1. Design

This study employed a descriptive correlational research approach to describe general education teachers' levels of readiness and perceived challenges in implementing inclusive education in selected SPED centers in Cebu Province, Philippines, and examine relationships between variables.

A descriptive correlational research design was well-suited for this study as it allowed for the description of characteristics of the population and examining relationships between variables (Morales, 2021). Descriptive correlational studies do not involve manipulating conditions, aligning with the objectives of describing teachers' perceived levels of readiness and challenges in implementing inclusion, and analyzing relationships between these variables and teacher profiles. Correlational designs are commonly used when exploring relationships between teacher perceptions or attributes and

implementation of educational practices (Mulyadi et al., 2023; Thomas, 2022). Similarly, this study aimed to examine connections between teacher perceptions of their own readiness and the barriers they faced promoting inclusion.

Considering multiple variables simultaneously through a correlational lens provided a more holistic view of the complex issue (Thomas, 2022). This addressed the multi-factorial nature of elements impacting inclusive education delivery from the teacher perspective. Furthermore, correlational research yielded meaningful insights informing targeted supports by identifying relationships between teacher qualities and implementation success (Morales, 2021). Likewise, the intended implications of the current study were to guide strategic capacity-building strategies based on findings. A descriptive correlational design was thus appropriately matched to address the objectives of understanding readiness barriers teachers faced from their own perspectives to ultimately translate insights into applicable recommendations.

The target population was all general education teachers from public elementary and high schools in identified SPED centers/schools in Cebu Province, Philippines. Simple random sampling was employed to select 25-38% of general education teachers from three SPED centers/schools identified in rural areas. A three-part, semi-structured online survey questionnaire via Google Forms was used for data collection.

Part 1 contained items on respondents' demographic profile including highest educational attainment, field of specialization, years of teaching experience, and relevant seminars or trainings attended. Part 2 assessed teachers' self-rated level of readiness across key areas of inclusive education using a 4-point Likert scale. Part 3 identified teachers' perceived challenges in implementing inclusive practices also utilizing a 4-point Likert scale.

The online questionnaire was distributed via email to sampled teachers. Responses were electronically submitted to Google Forms for compilation. This facilitated a streamlined collection process.

Descriptive statistics such as frequency, percentage, and weighted mean described the teacher profiles, readiness levels, and challenges. Pearson's *r* correlation determined relationships between teacher characteristics, readiness, and challenges.

This research design sought to develop a comprehensive picture of general education teachers' views and experiences in their local special education school settings, to generate meaningful insights and implications to inform practice.

2. Flow of the Study

This study aimed to understand general education teachers' levels of readiness and perceived challenges in implementing inclusive education in selected SPED centers in Cebu Province, Philippines. An IPO (Input- Process-Output) model (Figure 2) was utilized to efficiently conduct the research.

Input. The key inputs of the study included collecting data on teacher respondents' demographic profiles (e.g. age, gender, educational attainment, field of specialization, years of teaching experience, relevant trainings attended), their self-reported level of readiness towards inclusion, and perceived challenges in implementing inclusive education.

Process. The data gathered from the surveys and perception instruments underwent a systematic analysis process. Responses were coded and input into statistical software for descriptive and correlational analysis. This allowed the researchers to objectively describe patterns in the responses and identify relationships between variables. Findings were then interpreted through a theoretical framework.

Output. Valuable outputs resulted from rigorously processing the inputs through statistical procedures. The results revealed general education teachers' overall levels of readiness and main challenges faced in implementing inclusive education across different school contexts and demographic groups. Based on these findings, targeted recommendations could be developed to strengthen supports, trainings, and policies related to inclusive education reforms. Stakeholders gained actionable insights applicable for developing inclusion implementation plans tailored to address each school's specific needs and enhance teachers' readiness in supporting students with special educational needs in general education classrooms.

Figure 2. Flow of the Study

3. Instrument

A semi-structured survey questionnaire was developed for online administration via Google Forms to facilitate remote data collection from the respondents. The researchers adapted from adapted from the study of Larios et al. (2022) on the challenges to preparing teachers to instruct all students in inclusive classrooms and Sales (2019) on his study about the Concepts and Issues on Inclusive Education.

The questionnaire was divided into three sections. The first section collected demographic information from respondents, including their age, gender, highest educational attainment, field of specialization, and length of service. It also gathered data on relevant trainings and seminars attended.

This profile data provided context to understand teachers' perceived levels of readiness and challenges. The second section assessed teachers' self-reported level of readiness for implementing inclusive education using a 4-point Likert scale. The scale ratings were: 1) Not Ready, 2) Slightly Ready, 3) Ready, and 4) Very Ready. The third and final section examined the challenges encountered by teachers in supporting inclusive education. Respondents indicated their perceptions of challenge levels using another 4-point Likert scale, rated as: 1) Not Challenged, 2) Slightly Challenged, 3) Challenged, and 4) Extremely Challenged. Together, the three sections of the questionnaire provided both demographic context and quantitative data on teachers' perceived inclusionary skills and the difficulties faced, to comprehensively address the research aims.

4. Data Gathering Procedure

The study employed a quantitative research design using simple random sampling to select 104 teacher respondents from three schools in Cebu Province, Philippines: San Francisco Central School SPED Center, Liloan Central School, and Arcelo National High School. Specifically, the sample consisted of 26 teachers from San Francisco Central School SPED Center, 40 teachers from Liloan Central School, and 38 from Arcelo National High School, totaling 104 respondents.

Data collection was conducted over one week using an online survey questionnaire developed in Google Forms, allowing for remote and paperless administration in accordance with necessary health and safety protocols.

The researchers first obtained teacher email addresses from the selected schools and sent an informational email containing a description of the study, confidentiality assurances, and a link to the three-part questionnaire in Google Forms; teachers who provided consent by clicking the link were directed to respond electronically.

As responses were submitted, they were automatically compiled within Google Forms for ease of access and organization, while periodic reminders encouraged participation to maximize the response rate. This streamlined online format enabled efficient, remote distribution and collection of data across schools to understand teachers' perspectives on inclusion implementation.

5. Statistical Treatment of Data

Descriptive statistics were employed to analyze the data. Frequencies and percentages were used to characterize the demographic profile of respondents. Readiness levels were examined using frequency counts to understand patterns in teacher perceptions.

Challenges in inclusion implementation were assessed using a Likert scale. Weighted mean scores determined the most prominent difficulties faced to identify relationships between variables, inferential analysis was conducted.

Pearson's correlation coefficient (r) was calculated to measure the strength and direction of linear correlations between factors like educational background, experience, and training against readiness levels. Pearson's r ranges from -1 to 1, indicating the degree to which one variable changes about the other. This established that improvement in some areas correlated with increased perceived ability to support inclusive classrooms.

The statistical techniques allowed for systematically describing, comparing, and relating key elements in teachers' profiles and viewpoints, thereby addressing the research questions.

6. Scoring Procedures

The respondents responded to the three-section question. The first section incorporated the profile of the respondents as to age and gender; highest educational attainment; field of specialization; length of service; and relevant trainings attended. Second referred to the level of readiness towards inclusive education using a four-point Likert scale which was interpreted as follows: (1) not ready, (2) slightly ready, (3) ready, (4) very ready. The third section focused on the level of challenges met towards inclusive education using a four-point Likert scale which was interpreted as follows: (1) not challenged, (2) slightly challenged, (3) challenged, (4) extremely challenged.

This study subscribed to the following rubrics.

A. For interpreting the categorical responses of the respondent's level of readiness toward inclusive education.

Scale	Numerical Rating	Descriptive Rating	Verbal Interpretation
4	3.25-4.00	Very Ready	The respondents strongly agree on the statements describing their readiness on the implementation of inclusive education.
3	2.50-3.24	Ready	The respondents agree on the statements describing their readiness on the implementation of inclusive education.
2	1.75-2.49	Slightly Ready	The respondents disagree on the statements describing their readiness on the implementation of inclusive education.
1	1.00-1.74	Not Ready	The respondents strongly disagree on the statements describing their readiness on the implementation of inclusive education.

B. For interpreting the categorical responses of the respondent's level of challenges encountered on the implementation of inclusive education

Scale	Numerical Rating	Descriptive Rating	Verbal Interpretation
4	3.25-4.00	Extremely Challenged	The respondents strongly agree on the statements describing the challenges The encountered in the implementation of inclusive education.
3	2.50-3.24	Challenged	The respondents agree on the statements describing the challenges The encountered in the implementation of inclusive education.
2	1.75-2.49	Slightly Challenged	The respondents disagree on the statements describing the challenges The encountered in the implementation of inclusive education.
1	1.00-1.74	Not Challenged	The respondents strongly disagree on the statements describing the challenges The encountered in the implementation of inclusive education.

ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS & DATA PRIVACY

Participant privacy and confidentiality of data were strictly maintained through securely storing all paper and electronic information solely accessible to research team members. Personal details were not disclosed without obtaining consent. The study adhering to ethical standards, including attaining informed consent from all participants and upholding their right to withdraw at any point without facing repercussions. A systematic methodology supported robust data collection to examine general education teachers' perspectives on the readiness and challenges associated with implementing inclusive education. This involved implementing measures to ensure privacy, confidentiality, consent, and the right to withdraw, in order to gather data regarding teachers' views and experiences relating to their readiness and the challenges encountered when implementing inclusive education practices.

RESULTS

This section presented the results of the data analysis related to each research objective. The key findings from the teacher survey were outlined. Tables and descriptions showed patterns identified for variables like teacher backgrounds, readiness levels, challenges faced, and relationships between factors. The findings directly addressed the research questions. This provided a clear presentation of the evidence to inform conclusions and recommendations.

1. Respondent Profile

a. Age & Gender

Table 1
Age and Gender of the Respondents

Age (in years)	Female		Male		Total	
	f	%	f	%	f	%
48 and above	13	12.50	1	0.96	14	13.46
40-47	15	14.42	3	2.88	18	17.31
32-39	36	34.62	5	4.81	41	39.42
24-31	25	24.04	6	5.77	31	29.81
Total	89	85.58	15	14.42	104	100.00

Table 1 provided age and gender information of 104 respondents. It is shown that the majority of respondents were female, reflecting the gender composition of the teaching profession. Most fell within the 24-39 age range, representing mid-career teachers. Over two-thirds had pursued some graduate level education, obtaining at least a master's degree. However, the largest specialty areas of BEED and general education suggested qualifications could be strengthened with more direct training in specialization for inclusion. Teaching experience levels were moderately high, with most having 6-10 years. This indicated an experienced sample. INSET programs were the most commonly attended trainings. This profile depicted a sample of female, mid-career teachers with graduate degrees but room to grow specialization in inclusion-focused areas, relying on INSET for professional development. Overall, it represented an experienced yet developing profile suited to provide insights around inclusion practices.

The predominantly female gender distribution of teachers observed in this study mirrors broader patterns within the teaching profession in both the U.S. and Philippines (National Center for Education Statistics, 2023; Pentang et al., 2022; Northey, 2022). Data from the National Center for Education Statistics shows that females comprise approximately 77% of public school teachers in the

U.S. (National Center for Education Statistics, 2023). Similarly, research conducted in the Philippines found a disproportionate representation of females among educators (Pentang et al., 2022).

This marked overrepresentation of females among teachers has implications. Research by Delaney & Devereux (2021) and Bonefeld et al. (2022) found that the gender composition of educators can impact student achievement, especially in subjects like math. This suggested it was important to account for teachers' gender distribution when examining and addressing disparities in academic performance between student groups.

b. Highest Educational Attainment

Table 2
Respondents' Highest Educational Attainment

Educational Attainment	f	%
With Doctorate Units	2	1.92
Master's Graduate	11	10.58
With Master's Units	71	68.27
Bachelor's Degree	20	19.23
Total	104	100.00

An analysis of the highest educational qualifications of 104 teacher respondents was presented in Table 2. The distribution reflected a prevalence of Master's level education among the teacher respondents, aligning with the increasing pursuit of higher levels of education in recent years. The high prevalence of Master's level education among the teacher respondents was noteworthy. It may indicate a relatively well-educated cohort of teachers, which could potentially influence their readiness and ability to engage with the complexities of inclusive education (Gordon, 2023). Teachers with higher educational qualifications may possess a more advanced understanding of educational principles and practices, which could positively impact their preparedness for implementing inclusive education initiatives (Opoku et al., 2022).

This finding also underscored the importance of considering the educational background of teachers when examining their readiness and challenges in implementing inclusive education. It suggested that the majority of the teacher respondents have a solid educational foundation, which could be leveraged to support the successful integration of inclusive education practices within their teaching environments.

c. Field of Specialization

Table 3
Field of Specialization of the Respondents

Field of Specialization	f	%
Administration and Supervision	3	2.88
ALS-Multi	1	0.96
BEED	16	15.38

Early Childhood Education	4	3.85
General Education	11	10.58
SPED	10	9.62
English	9	8.65
Filipino	9	8.65
Math	9	8.65
Science	7	6.73
Social Studies	5	4.81
TLE	13	12.50
Religious Education	1	0.96
Values Education	1	0.96
No Response	5	4.81
Total	104	100.00

The academic specializations held by 104 participating teachers were described in Table 3. It shown that the majority of teachers from the selected SPED Center/schools specialized in either Basic Elementary Education (BEED) or other general elementary education subjects. This indicated that their initial teacher education programs may not have adequately prepared them for inclusive practices through specialized inclusion training (Singogo & Muzata, 2023). BEED and generalist-focused programs potentially did not equip teachers with strategies for differentiating instruction, classroom management skills for diverse learners, or collaboration skills needed for inclusive models (Singogo & Muzata, 2023).

Few teachers specialized in areas like early childhood education, administration/supervision, or special education, meaning there were limited teachers with expertise to support inclusion through learning strategies or knowledge of exceptionalities (Faragher et al., 2021). This aligned with prior research finding that insufficient training and guidance from specialists created barriers to inclusion (Faragher et al., 2021).

The dominant generalist academic backgrounds revealed provided context for the readiness gaps and implementation challenges reported (Singogo & Muzata, 2023). Targeted inclusion training throughout teachers' careers, particularly for BEED and general elementary teachers, may have been necessary to truly prepare them for their key roles in inclusive classrooms (Singogo & Muzata, 2023).

d. Length of Service

Table 4
Length of Service of Respondents

Length of Service (in years)	f	%
16 and above	18	17.31
11-15	12	11.54
6-10	45	43.27

1-5	29	27.88
Total	104	100.00

Information on the teaching experience levels of 104 teacher respondents was detailed in Table 4. Most of the surveyed teachers had a moderate level of experience falling in the 6-10 years range, while another one-fourth had fewer years of 1-5. Relatively fewer had over 15 years of teaching service. The studies of Brussino (2021) and Abrazado et al. (2021) suggested that teachers' length of service as shown in Table 4, can influence their attitudes towards inclusive education. Other studies have found that teachers with longer service were more likely to believe that inclusive education requires a selective approach (Radojlovic et al., 2022) according to the type and severity of disabilities.

The findings from these studies suggested that a teacher's length of experience may influence their perspective on inclusion, with more veteran teachers more likely to support a selective approach or express positive views. To help foster positive attitudes among new teachers, it was crucial to emphasize high-quality inclusive education training as a core part of initial teacher preparation programs. Additional supports may also be necessary to help experienced instructors successfully adopt inclusive practices as policies and understandings of students' needs continue developing over the years. Ensuring both new and experienced teachers received the training and resources needed to implement inclusion well can help all students receive an education that meets their needs.

e. Relevant Trainings and Seminars Attended

Table 5
Relevant Trainings and Seminars Attended by the Respondents

Trainings and Seminars Attended	f	Rank
INSET	67	1
Seminar on Inclusive Education	7	2
Training of Filipino Sign Language	3	3
Capacity Building Seminar in SPED	1	4.5
Seminar on Multi-factored Assessment tool	1	4.5

*multiple response

Table 5 provided information on the various relevant trainings and seminars that the 104 teacher respondents had attended in the past, based on their multiple responses. It displayed the distribution of their responses across five different training/seminar options and ranked them based on the frequency with which the teachers reported attending each program. By far the training that the largest number of teachers had participated in was the INSET (In-Service Education and Training), with 67 teachers (64.42% of total responses) indicating they had attended INSET programs before. This suggests INSET was the most commonly available and accessed form of professional development.

The second most attended program that some teachers had participated in was a seminar focused specifically on Inclusive Education, with 7 teacher responses (6.73% of total) reporting attendance. A training workshop in Filipino Sign Language came next with 3 teachers (2.88% of responses) stating they had attended it. Only one teacher each had participated in more specialized seminars on Multi-factored Assessment tools for students and Capacity Building related to Special Education needs. This represented just 0.96% of responses each. Notably, INSET ranked far ahead of other options in terms of the number of teachers who had participated in the past. More niche topics

saw much lower uptake. This provided insight into the relative popularity and spread of different professional development formats available to these in-service teachers. The literature (Crispel & Kasperski, 2021; Wray et al., 2022) suggested that ongoing professional learning opportunities, such as targeted training and seminars (Table 5), were essential for enhancing teacher readiness and efficacy in implementing inclusive education strategies. The study of Eklund et al. (2021) showed educators lacked competence in supporting students facing academic challenges and were not adequately prepared to address diverse learning needs. Therefore, it was crucial to provide relevant and appropriate professional development to strengthen teachers' capabilities for cultivating quality, inclusive classrooms.

The research of Ismailos et al. (2022), Lualhati (2022), and Quilapio & Callo (2022) also indicated professional development courses could help pre-service and in-service teachers improve both practical skills and attitudes toward successfully supporting disabilities. It was recommended that mainstream schools worked collaboratively across the educational system to become truly inclusive through combined efforts. Ancho & Arrieta (2021) emphasized the importance of making available meaningful professional learning opportunities on an ongoing basis. This allowed teachers to increase their readiness and ability to execute inclusion best practices. By addressing barriers hindering teacher preparedness through high-quality professional development, the literature suggested it was possible to improve inclusive education quality and ensure all students received accommodating, supportive environments where their needs were met. Addressing lack of teacher competence appeared key to unlocking inclusive education's full benefits.

2. Level of Readiness

Table 6 presented findings regarding the self-rated levels of readiness reported by teacher respondents from the selected SPED Center/Schools toward the implementation of inclusive education.

Table 6
Level of readiness of the respondents towards the implementation of inclusive education

S/N	Indicators	WM	Verbal Description
1	Most days, I am prepared to teach learners with disabilities in my general education class.	2.82	Ready
2	I am given adequate training and resources to understand the IEP and its components.	2.50	Ready
3	I am given to adequate time to collaborate with Special Education Teachers.	2.49	Slightly Ready
4	I feel that I get adequate support to teach students with disabilities from Special Education Teachers, Para Educators (Assistants), and my School Administrative Staff.	2.48	Slightly Ready
5	I am aware of the laws that protect the learners with disabilities.	2.99	Ready
6	I understand the rules and responsibilities of special and general education teachers in inclusive classroom.	2.91	Ready
7	I have adequate trainings on how to handle learners with disabilities in my class.	2.34	Slightly Ready
8	I have the skills to implement the IEP for learners with disabilities in my class.	2.27	Slightly Ready
	Aggregate Weighted Mean	2.60	Ready

Legend: 3.25-4.00-Very Ready; 2.50- 3.24- Ready ;1.75 - 2.49-Slightly Ready ; 1.00 - 1.74- Not Ready

Teachers rated their own readiness for inclusion as "Ready" but with a mean score of only 2.60, indicating they were just above the midpoint of "Slightly Ready". Mean scores for key applied skills of collaboration, training, and IEP development were even lower at around 2.5 and 2.3, firmly in the "Slightly Ready" range. While teachers felt generally prepared for inclusion, they reported needing more targeted support to develop essential applied skills critical for implementation. This suggested initial training programs may not have adequately prepared teachers for the practical aspects of inclusion. Over two-thirds had postgraduate education but predominantly in fields like BEED and general education rather than specializations directly related to inclusion. The moderate overall readiness rating coupled with lower scores for applied skills indicated qualifications could be strengthened to provide more direct preparation.

In summary, teachers saw themselves as ready for inclusion in theory but identified clear needs for developing important collaborative, training, and IEP skills through more targeted support. Their backgrounds likewise pointed to room for initial programs to better prepare teachers practically.

3. Level of Challenges

Table 7 presented the results on the level of challenges encountered by teacher respondents from the selected SPED Center/Schools in implementing inclusive education. Understanding difficulties faced provided crucial insights for addressing barriers to effective inclusion.

Table 7
Level of challenges encountered by the respondents on the implementation of inclusive education

S/N	Indicators	WM	Verbal Description
1	Lack of special education teachers	3.38	Extremely Challenged
2	Lack of facilities for special care	3.46	Extremely Challenged
3	Lack of special education classes	3.38	Extremely Challenged
4	Lack of appropriate resources	3.38	Extremely Challenged
5	Inappropriate allocation of learning materials	3.13	Challenged
6	Lack of understanding of inclusive education	2.98	Challenged
7	Inadequate program for teacher's development	3.02	Challenged
8	Absence of working relationship between parents and school	2.72	Challenged
9	Lack of communication with parents	2.65	Challenged
10	Unsupportive school board/school governing council	2.60	Challenged
Aggregate Weighted Mean		3.07	Challenged

Legend: 3.25-4.00-Extremely Challenged; 2.50- 3.24-Challenged ;1.75 - 2.49-Slightly Challenged ;1.00 -1.74- Not Challenged

Teachers rated the overall level of challenges to inclusion implementation as "Challenged", with a mean score of 3.07. However, they identified significant resource shortages as major obstacles that were rated as even more challenging. The lack of key resources like specialized teachers, suitable

facilities and classrooms, and appropriate learning materials were perceived to present extreme challenges, with mean scores falling in the highest "Extremely Challenged" range between 3.38-3.46. Systemic resource shortages, particularly in terms of specialized human resources and adequate infrastructure, posed the greatest challenges according to teachers. This indicated inclusion efforts faced major barriers due to gaps at the systemic level that required urgent upgrades. While implementation challenges were viewed as challenging overall, a lack of fundamental supports was seen as an extremely formidable hindrance. Significant upgrades were needed to provide baseline resources like trained personnel, adapted facilities and learning aids in order to overcome the most pressing obstacles identified.

4. Relationship between Readiness and Challenges

Table 8 presented the results of the statistical test that was conducted to determine if there was a significant relationship between the levels of readiness and challenges that the 104 teacher respondents had reported facing in the past implementation of inclusive education programs.

Table 8
Test of significant relationship between the readiness and challenges encountered by the respondents on the implementation of inclusive education

Variables	r-value	Strength of Correlation	p - value	Decision	Result
Readiness and Challenges	0.003	Negligible Positive	0.976	Do not reject Ho	Not Significant

The study examined the potential relationship between teachers' self-reported readiness levels for inclusion implementation and their perceptions of challenges faced. While both readiness deficits and obstacles existed to some degree, the statistical analysis found only a negligible positive correlation ($r = 0.003$) between these two variables. Additionally, the p-value of 0.976 exceeded the critical value, indicating no statistically significant relationship.

This suggested that for this sample of teachers, their perceived levels of preparedness did not strongly predict the challenges they reported, and vice versa. In other words, readiness deficits and obstacles did not appear to influence one another to a large degree.

The lack of a clear predictive relationship implied that multi-faceted solutions targeting both teachers' qualifications as well as systemic resource barriers may have been necessary. A one-dimensional approach focusing solely on either readiness improvements or challenges alone may not have sufficiently addressed the complexity of factors involved.

Overall, the negligible correlation ($r = 0.003$) between variables and non-significant relationship ($p > 0.05$) suggested a more comprehensive strategy was warranted to strengthen inclusion implementation, rather than assuming ameliorating one issue would naturally alleviate the other. Both pre-service training and systemic support upgrades may have been important concurrently.

CONCLUSION

This study examined teachers' perceptions of their readiness to implement inclusive education and the challenges they faced. While teachers felt generally prepared in theory, the findings provided

valuable insights into needs for strengthened qualifications and systemic support upgrades. The results indicated that key issues needed to be addressed to enhance inclusion efforts.

Specifically, teachers could benefit from more targeted training in inclusion-focused areas as initial programs may not have fully equipped them with practical skills. Resource shortages, especially specialized personnel and infrastructure, posed major barriers requiring systemic improvements. According to the teachers, their qualifications and access to resources were important factors influencing implementation.

Additionally, the lack of a clear relationship between readiness factors and challenges indicated a multi-pronged approach was necessary. Both enhancing pre-service preparation and investing in foundational supports were important to facilitate implementation efforts. The findings suggested readiness and challenges did not solely depend on one another, implying the need for a holistic solution.

The insights reflected the complexity of factors involved and the need for comprehensive solutions concurrently strengthening qualifications through ongoing professional development, while also overcoming pressing resource obstacles via coordinated reforms across education levels. A long-term, multi-level strategy appeared warranted. To translate these conclusions into practical action, the following recommendations are proposed: (1) Reform initial teacher training to provide specialized inclusion content and applied skill-building opportunities. Tailoring preparation programs could help address identified gaps. (2) Invest in ongoing professional development focused on collaborative skills, IEP development, specialized training, and sharing best practices. Continuous skills upgrading was viewed as important. (3) Upgrade systemic supports by allocating resources for specialized teachers, adapted facilities and classrooms, and appropriate learning materials. Addressing barriers could aid implementation. (4) Facilitate multi-level coordination between educators, administrators, policymakers and stakeholders to implement holistic, long-term inclusion strategies. Cooperation across sectors was crucial. (5) Establish collaborative networks for educators to learn from each other's experiences in overcoming readiness deficits and challenges. Sharing insights could strengthen inclusion efforts over time.

With commitment to addressing needs through the above comprehensive, multi-pronged strategy simultaneously targeting readiness improvements and barrier removal, inclusion practices could be substantially strengthened based on insights gleaned from educators. Their perspectives highlight the importance of targeted yet collaborative solutions.

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